

ONE SHOT MANUFACTURING OF A HIGHLY INTEGRATED STRUCTURE BY AUTOMATIC LAMINATION WITH THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

During the last years, the benefits of using carbon reinforced thermoplastic composite materials (CRTP) have been questioned and defended (enumerating some benefits: higher fatigue resistance, greater toughness, better durability, reprocessability, recyclability and so on), they are considered as a future innovative technology allowing highly integrated structures, impacting in weight reduction and reducing energetic costs by using out of autoclave processes. Therefore, (CRTP) could be considered as a future substitute of metallic materials and composite materials based on thermoset matrices for aerospace applications, automotive and other industries.

Under the frame of the OUTCOME project (Clean Sky II), the design and analysis of the Upper Skin (upper coverage of a stiffened wing) for the military aircraft C295 is developed, a medium tactical transport aircraft of Airbus Defence and Space (ADS).

The selected material for the work is the unidirectional composite material APC2/AS4, supplied by Solvay, with PEEK as the thermoplastic matrix and carbon fibre as the reinforcement. Flat panels, detailed elementals and sub-elementals have been manufactured; all of them have been widely characterized attempting to obtain the required design allowable.

Moreover, with the goal of cost reduction, productivity increases and environmental impact control, the manufacturing selected processes were: a) Hot-forming in oven and/or self- heated toolings for stringers manufacturing and b) Automatic lamination in one step for the co-consolidation (full-integration) of the skin with the stringers.

This review shows the different applied steps to manufacture a detailed element for a later structural test.

1 INTRODUCTION

Considering the development of aircraft structural parts, automatic lamination with thermoplastics composite materials is presented as a new potential alternative. The main benefits by applying this technology are related to the cost and time reduction by manufacturing highly integrated structures that do not require secondary consolidation steps in autoclave or oven.

The lack of maturity at the process, the slow development of thermoplastics matrices (PEEK, PEKK, PEI) and the absence of data to define the design allowable are some of the factors blocking the application into structural parts.

Design allowable are determined by mechanical testing, physical and chemical analysis and a complete dimensional inspection. Whilst this characterization is performed following a testing pyramid, a specific manufacturing process has been studied for the stiffeners following a T-shape geometry with the goal of generating a T-shape stiffeners/stringer to be used for a future integration in detail structures, sub-elements and final demonstrators.

2 OBJECTIVE

In the OUTCOME project (Clean Sky II), one of the targeted activities consists in obtaining a highly integrated part with thermoplastic composite materials and without using the autoclave. Particularly, the selected structure lies in an upper skin cover for the military aircraft C295.

Figure 1: Design scheme of a thermoplastic “Upper Skin”

Trying to reach this goal, a complete structural testing pyramid is carried out. The results are used by design, analysis and qualification departments in ADS (Airbus Defense and Space) in order to specify the load resistance capabilities of the final part. The part will be finally checked by ground and flight tests.

Figure 2: Structural testing pyramid

This document globally describes each step of the testing pyramid, focusing on the manufacturing processes for elementals and its integration. The structure ‘skin panel compression’ will be used as an example to describe the associated activities.

3 EXPERIMENTAL

3.1 Materials

The material used in this work consists of a carbon reinforced unidirectional tape manufactured by Solvay and coded APC2/AS4. It is composed by carbon fiber reinforcement, AS4 and a high performance semi-crystalline thermoplastic polymer, PEEK.

The APC2/AS4 material is supplied in two different formats: a) 1/4” width spools for automatic fiber placement lamination activities and 0.135mm thickness, and b) 300 mm width spools for hand lay-up activities and with the same former thickness.

Both materials have a resin percentage of a 34% in mass and a density of 1.32g/cm³. The fiber density equals 1.79g/cm³ and the fiber areal weight is 145 g/cm².

3.2 Characterization

For each of the manufactured elementals and demonstrators, control coupons have been done in order to guarantee its final quality. All the tests have been conducted in FIDAMC facilities as well as the preliminary sample preparation. The aforementioned tests are listed below:

- Mechanical testing by means of Plain Compression (PC) and Plain Tension (PT) performed in a 100kN Universal Testing Machine MTS.
- Physical and chemical testing by means of voids content (V%), crystallinity ($\alpha\%$) and optical microscopy.
 - o Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) has been used to determine the processing temperatures and also for obtaining the final crystallization percentages developed by the parts. The measured average values were 330°C for the extrapolated melting onset, 348°C for the melting peak and 35% for the degree of crystallization. The equipment that has been employed was a TA Instruments Q2000 model.
 - o Void content has been determined by two different methodologies: a) density method by using a Mettler Toledo XP205DR balance and b) acid digestion procedure.
 - o The optical microscopic analysis has been conducted in accordance to the standard AITM 4-0005.

3.3 Equipment

For the stiffeners manufacturing process, an IDEC oven has been used with an IAC control system. This equipment has a wide temperature working range, permitting to develop cycles up to 450°C.

The flat panels for process characterization, the control coupons and the skins have been manufactured by a multiple-tow lamination machine (Figure 3). The head contains a heating system by means of a LASERLINE diode laser with fix optics and with a homogenizer. The laser wavelength is in the range between 900 to 1070 nm. It is required a heating source with a high efficiency and energy to permit the modifications of the required area. For the temperature control, a close loop control system has been developed and implemented by FIDAMC. The spools are also placed in the head of the machine, a total number of 8.

Figure 3: Thermoplastic AFP multiple-tow.

4 MANUFACTURING PROCESS

All the developments in the frame of OUTCOME project to obtain the final part (upper skin panel) have been possible thanks to a concurrent engineering between ADS and FIDAMC.

4.1 Testing pyramid

The testing campaign of the coupons for laminae properties and for the characteristic laminates has been done by FIDAMC including manufacturing of the components, specimens' preparation and the tests, the analysis has been lately done by ADS.

The campaigns have been done with different temperature (RT, 70 °C and 120 °C) and humidity conditions.

Figure 4: Detail of failure mode for bolted joint specimens.

Stringer Crippling (Figure 5) and Stringer Run Out Detail, have been produced as the secondary step in the testing pyramid.

A total number of 12 specimens of Stringer Crippling configuration need to be manufactured with two different configurations: thick and thin (concerning the layers number). Half of them have been tested at room temperature conditions and the rest in Hot/Wet conditions.

Figure 5: Crippling coupon.

For testing the Stringer Run Out Detail, 7 specimens are required. The first of them has been used to determine the impact energy and the remaining six have been tested half at room conditions and the other half in Hot/Wet (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Stringer run out coupon.

In parallel to the manufacturing process of testing specimens, the stringers production and the positioned of the first layer for automated lamination were adjusted.

4.2 Stringers manufacturing of *compression skin panel*

All the stringers employed in the development of this project have a T-shape with different lamination sequence, section changes and thicknesses.

The general manufacturing process is composed by eight steps which are detailed below:

1. Tooling design.
2. Tooling manufacturing.
3. Hand lay-up of skins which form every “L”
4. Consolidation in oven of “Ls”.
5. Manufacturing of the fillers in hot-plate press.
6. Integration of L-shapes to generate a “H”.
7. Trimming
8. Ultrasonic and dimensional inspection.

Tooling is designed and manufactured according with the structural part requirements. Afterwards, the stacking sequence of the “Ls” is laminated over a flat plate joining the patterns by means of welding points to allow the movement between layers in the oven consolidation process.

“Ls” are consolidated in a single oven cycle and at the same time; fillers are formed in press (*Press forming*). The material of the fillers is the same than for the rest of components.

An assembly is performed, in “H”, with four “Ls” and with the fillers to obtain the final geometry. In each execution, two stringers are extracted.

4.3 Skin lamination by in-situ consolidation (ISC)

The tooling employed for the integration has two notable systems: (a) Vacuum system which helps to fix the first layer and subsequent fastening of the part during the lamination and (b) Heating system which allows lightening part of the residual stresses inherent to the lamination process.

Once the stringers have been trimmed and inspected, a surface treatment by means of sanding is carried out in order to increase the adhesion in the lamination of the first layer. After this stage, stringers are positioned over the tooling in such a way that the first layer is laminated over the stringers’ foot. Once stringers are sanded and positioned, a PEEK film is place to improve the joint by means of consolidation.

The skin/lining is automatically laminated with an AFP multiple-tow machine and in this particular case, six tows and a 1 m/ min of lamination speed were employed.

4.4 NDT test

Once the piece has been demolded and trimmed (Figure 7), a non-destructive inspection by means of ultrasound with a pulse-echo technique was applied (Figure 8).

Figure 7: Demolding of skin panel compression.

Figure 8: C-Scan of manufactured specimens

Finally, a dimensional analysis was performed: thicknesses, dimensions related to positioned, strains.

4.5 Destructive tests

The lamination of the skin and control coupons was developed at the same time. These control coupons are employed to perform mechanical tests of plain compression (PC), plain tension (PT) and physic-chemical tests (extent of crystallinity, void content and microscopic evaluation).

5 CONCLUSIONS

One shot automated lamination technology without subsequent re-consolidation steps in autoclave is a fact for both flat panels for testing and stiffened substructures.

Values obtained in the *skin panel compression* characterization showed that its quality is optimal to test.

The current difficult when the size of the piece increases are the residual stresses inherent to the ISC process which generate certain deformation in final parts. This problem is considered as a future work to develop in FIDAMC.

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